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A consistency measure for psychometric measurements

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ABSTRACT:

Adaptive tracking procedures in psychophysics may produce erroneous, “untypical” results and non-converging tracks due to, e.g., inattention of the test subject or external disturbances. This paper presents a multi-state psychometric model, which is used to rate the outcome of psychometric measurement procedures with a consistency measure. The consistency measure may be used for a *post hoc*, automated consistency estimation for any psychometric measurement procedure that can be modeled with a sigmoid psychometric function. The model calculates the log likelihood difference between single and two interleaved psychometric functions, potentially underlying a recorded adaptive track. A binary classifier was tested with a range of candidates for consistency measures with simulated, inconsistent tracks, and expert ratings of empirical tracks. The proposed consistency measure was identified as the best candidate to classify inconsistent tracks, while expert ratings were best predicted with the spectrum of the stimulus level, which is shown to be a suboptimal predictor of consistency. A threshold of the proposed measure for the German matrix sentence test is 10 to test for inconsistency, with a sensitivity of 60% and a specificity of 80%.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The assessment of psychophysical thresholds [such as, e.g., pure tone detection or the speech recognition threshold (SRT)] is a fundamental task in psychometrics with many applications in hearing science or audiology. Numerous psychometric measurement procedures have been defined with the goal of optimizing the reliability of the measurement for a given time spent on the task (Treutwein, 1995; Leek, 2001).

In the following, we define the term “consistency” of a psychometric test to describe how much the experimental results match the underlying assumptions of the experimenter. Traditionally, the consistency of the outcome of a psychometric test is considered a direct consequence of the applied procedure, i.e., the occurrence of inconsistent measurements is minimized with the most appropriate measurement procedure. However, the consistency is typically not checked and quantified during a listening experiment. It remains the task of the experimenter to assess the consistency of the outcome of the procedure he or she has chosen. If the consistency is unsatisfactory, the measurement procedure is altered, e.g., with a retest, break, termination, etc. However, this consistency rating remains highly subjective and prone to mistakes, depending on, e.g., the visual representation of the data or the experience of the experimenter with the testing procedure.

We describe a *post hoc* model that can be used to assess the consistency of measurement data (in the following called

track) with the common assumption of a single psychometric function. The model can be used to monitor the consistency of a psychometric measurement with an objective, easy-to-interpret scalar value. The aim of this paper is not to define a new type of adaptive procedure that is more robust in difficult listening conditions [see, for instance, Xu *et al.* (2024)], but rather to quantify the consistency of the respective test results. The model is implemented for, but not limited to, the matrix sentence test (Kollmeier *et al.*, 2015) as a PYTHON package and supplements this work.

A. Suboptimal measurement conditions

Fully remote and self-administered e-health systems with audiological tests (Swanepoel *et al.*, 2010; Ooster *et al.*, 2020; Swanepoel and Hall, 2010) require robust and fast psychometric measurements. In uncontrolled environments, the outcome of these measurements is subject to internal and external variation.

- Internal variations are changes in attention of the test subject, e.g., messaging services on the same device causing a slip in attention [short-term inattention according to Xu *et al.* (2024)] or exhaustion with permanently decreased attention [long-term inattention, according to Xu *et al.* (2024)].
- External variations are sudden changes in the performance of the measurement equipment during an experiment, like a forced change in volume or a change of background noise. These continuously alter the measurement condition.

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The two types of variation suggest that under suboptimal measurement conditions, the psychometric function, connecting response probability to the stimulus, differs from the standard sigmoid function. This may result in a shift of the threshold after a lasting change in attention during the measurement (Bianco *et al.*, 2021) or a nonstationary psychometric function (Frund *et al.*, 2011).

B. Problem statement

In the following, we define the outcome of a psychometric measurement as a sequence of stimuli (\mathbf{s}) together with a sequence of responses (\mathbf{r}), called track, with N numbered values of presentation and corresponding response, called trial, during the test:

$$\mathbf{s} = \{s_0, s_1, \dots, s_{N-1}\}, \quad s_n \in \mathbf{s}, \tag{1}$$

$$\mathbf{r} = \{r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{N-1}\}, \quad r_n \in \mathbf{r}. \tag{2}$$

Every trial may consist of several test items in immediate succession. Each corresponds to a binary decision together with its evaluation [e.g., correctly heard/classified (hit) vs not heard or incorrectly classified (miss)].

The reason for this distinction between trial and test item is that the responses to the test items inside a trial are given together, and that the time between test items is much smaller than the time between trials. The transition probability for change of the psychometric function may differ substantially between trials and between the test items inside a trial. Our definition assumes that the psychometric function only changes between trials and that the transition between test items can be neglected.

The general assumption is that the response as a function of the corresponding stimulus is scattered around a sigmoid function. This function is referred to as the psychometric function.

As an example, consider the track of a matrix sentence test (Kollmeier *et al.*, 2015) in Fig. 1. The closed matrix sentence test contains 20 sentences and a test-specific masking noise. Here, a trial with index n is a sentence in noise at a signal-to-noise level of s_n . The trial consists of five syntactically fixed, random words (i.e., test items of the sentence), which have ten alternatives each. This way, the rate of correctly answered trials \mathbf{r} is measured in discrete steps of 0.2. The guess rate, which is the chance of a random, correctly identified trial, is equal to 0.1 (see Appendix A). Because r_n is the average of five Bernoulli experiments, it is a sample of a

FIG. 1. Adaptive track of an inconsistent psychometric measurement The most likely single- and two-state models are indicated in green and blue/orange, respectively. The upper panel plots the sequence of responses (\mathbf{r}) of the test subject against the sequence of stimuli (\mathbf{s}). The index n of the trial is written next to each entry. Psychometric functions are indicated with solid lines; the standard deviation of the binomial distribution is indicated with broken lines. The lower panel shows the same measurement as a function of n with the response indicated next to the entry. Here, the broken line shows the estimated threshold (SRT) according to the single-state psychometric function (Brand and Kollmeier, 2002).

binomial distribution around the value of the psychometric function at the corresponding s_n (see upper panel of Fig. 1).

At the beginning of a matrix test ($n = 0$), the first trial is presented to the test subject with the stimulus level s_0 and the initial response r_0 is recorded. The measurement procedure defines the next stimulus s_{n+1} , conditioned on all previous stimuli and responses. The procedure repeats until an ending criterion is met (see upper panel of Fig. 2). The track (s and r) of the matrix test is stored for later analysis.

We need a consistency measure of the track that fulfills the following requirements:

- (1) It has to be a scalar measure and thereby easy to interpret.
- (2) The measure should indicate how well the track matches the assumption of a single psychometric function.
- (3) The measure should be fast and easy to use.
- (4) If properties of the expected psychometric function (e.g., guess rate, average slope) are known, these should be included in the calculation to improve the results.

Because of the way this measure is defined, we will refer to it as the single psychometric function goodness of fit measure (SiPGOF).

II. METHODS

A. Model definition

In this study, a subject of a psychometric measurement is modeled by a Markov process. Each Markov state is

associated with a psychometric function (see lower panel of Fig. 2). The psychometric function is commonly described with the four parameter transformed logistic model [see, for example, Doire *et al.* (2017)]. These four parameters are the lapse rate (λ), guess rate (γ), and α as well as β , that determine the threshold (SRT for matrix sentence tests) and slope at the threshold

$$\Phi(s) = \gamma + \frac{1 - \gamma - \lambda}{1 + \exp(-\beta(s - \alpha))}. \quad (3)$$

The simplest model of this type is a single-state with only one psychometric function and no state transitions with a total of 4 degrees of freedom. We refer to this as the single-state model. This model is equivalent to the model of Brand and Kollmeier (2002).

With two states, the model has two psychometric functions (one for each state $i = 0, i = 1$), the probability distribution of the first state π and the 2×2 transition matrix A . A describes the probability $p(i \rightarrow i')$ for all possible transitions of the current state i to the next state i' (see lower panel of Fig. 2),

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} p(0 \rightarrow 0) & p(0 \rightarrow 1) \\ p(1 \rightarrow 0) & p(1 \rightarrow 1) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{00} & a_{01} \\ a_{10} & a_{11} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

These two states may be interpreted as a state of concentration and a state of distraction, and we refer to this in the following as a two-state model. It has 8 degrees of freedom if the two psychometric functions only differ in threshold (i.e., two thresholds, one slope, γ, λ , transition matrix with two degrees of freedom, π with one degree of freedom). A maximum of 11 degrees of freedom is possible if the two psychometric functions differ in all four parameters.

Note that it is crucial to keep the number of free parameters of the model as small as possible, as overfitting might occur for short tracks. For the matrix sentence test considered here, a track consists of $N = 20$ trials. For this reason, we chose the following strict boundary conditions: the slope was fixed to the average slope of the considered matrix test, λ was set to zero, and γ was set to the theoretical 0.1 for closed tests. This led to a two-state model with five degrees of freedom and a single state model with one degree of freedom.

1. Model fit to tracks

The single-state and two-state versions of the model were used to calculate the maximum likelihood across the model parameters for a given track. For this, we initialized the free parameters of both models with default values and optimized for the likelihood. The optimization worked as follows.

For each state i of the model, with corresponding psychometric function Φ_i : given a response r_k to a stimulus s_k , we compute the likelihood, or emission probability, $p_{i,k}$ that r_k was the result of a Bernoulli experiment with $H = r_k \cdot T$

FIG. 2. Model of responses to an adaptive measurement procedure. Top: Workflow of the simulation of inconsistent tracks. From the previous stimuli s_k and responses $r_0, r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k$, the adaptive procedure defines a new stimulus s_{k+1} , which is presented to the subject to trigger the next response r_{k+1} . The loop repeats until an ending criterion is met. Bottom: A subject may have several internal states with different psychometric functions (bottom right example for the matrix sentence test). A Markov process models the state transitions with a transition matrix (bottom left). The row index is the current state and the column index is the next state [see Eq. (4)]. Depending on the current state, the probability of a correct response is given by the psychometric function of that state.

hits out of T test items ($T = 5$ words in case of the matrix test),

$$p_{i,k} = \binom{T}{H} (\Phi_i(s_k))^H \cdot (1 - \Phi_i(s_k))^{T-H}. \tag{5}$$

The multi-state model parameters are optimized using the expectation maximization (EM)/Baum-Welch algorithm [Bishop (2009), Chap. 13.2] (Rabiner, 1989). The likelihood of the model is calculated with the forward algorithm. The free parameters of the psychometric functions (model states) are updated using a standard function in the Scipy optimization library (Virtanen *et al.*, 2020). If properties of the expected psychometric function are known, these are included as a boundary condition. All computational details are documented in the code supplement Scharf (2025). The resulting maximum log-likelihood (l_{\max}) quantifies how well the model can describe the track, assuming the local optimum is equal to the global optimum

$$l_{\max} = \max_{\gamma, \lambda, \alpha, \beta, \dots} (l). \tag{6}$$

We define SiPGOF as the l_{\max} difference between the single- and two-state models

$$\text{SiPGOF} = l_{\max, \text{two-state}} - l_{\max, \text{single-state}}. \tag{7}$$

This means that SiPGOF assigns a value to a track

$$\text{SiPGOF}: (\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{r}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}. \tag{8}$$

Small values indicate agreement with a single-state model, and large values indicate good agreement with the two-state model.

2. Monte Carlo simulation of tracks

For the first part of the study, a simplified model (with fewer free parameters than for fitting) was used to simulate inconsistent adaptive tracks of the matrix sentence test. These tracks were used to test candidates for consistency measures. A fully controllable model with known internal states made it possible to quantify consistency [i.e., the mismatch between the estimated psychometric threshold and the threshold of the model, referred to as known inconsistency (KIC), see definition below] and compare it with candidates for a measure of consistency.

We initialized the model with psychometric functions Φ_i from literature values. A was parameterized by a single variable $a = a_{00} = a_{11}$ (i.e., the probability to stay in the same state),

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a & 1 - a \\ 1 - a & a \end{pmatrix}. \tag{9}$$

This was done to reduce the number of model parameters. It reflects the assumption that transitions between states are equally likely, an effect that is commonly observed

during measurements as “losing the cue,” i.e., a situation where a subject continuously stays distracted with probability $a_{01} = a_{10} = 1 - a$ after a seldom occurring distraction. The initial state i of Eq. (4) was initialized randomly to remove any bias towards one of the states in the Markov chain.

Provided with an initial stimulus s_0 , the model returned the probability of a correct response for each item of a trial according to the psychometric function Φ_i of the current internal state i [see Eq. (3)].

With this probability, the response r_0 of a subject was simulated (Monte Carlo). r_0 was then fed as input to the measurement procedure to compute the next stimulus s_1 (see upper panel of Fig. 2). This repeated until the procedure terminated with $N = 20$ trials. The result was a simulation of an inconsistent track for which the hidden states were known.

Artificial tracks numbering 50×10^3 were generated this way with average psychometric slopes for Cantonese and US-English matrix sentence tests of 14.25%/dB (Kollmeier *et al.*, 2015; Hu *et al.*, 2024), $\lambda = 0$, threshold differences of the two psychometric functions (in steps of 1 dB in the range from 0 to 4 dB) and parametrization of the transition matrix a (in 10 equidistant steps for values between 0 and 1) of the transition matrix. The initial stimulus value of the adaptive procedure was set to $s_0 = 0$ dB.

The generated database contained fully consistent (threshold difference = 0 dB or $a = 1$) and highly inconsistent tracks (threshold difference > 0 dB and $a \neq 1$) to test candidates for consistency measures. The internal states of every simulated track were used to define the KIC.

3. KIC of simulated tracks

We define the scalar KIC of a matrix test as the smallest absolute threshold difference ΔSRT_i between the SRT of either one of the two states i and the estimated $\text{SRT}_{\text{estim}}$ of a simulated track

$$\Delta\text{SRT}_i = \text{SRT}_i - \text{SRT}_{\text{estim}}, \tag{10}$$

$$\text{KIC} = \min_{|\Delta\text{SRT}|} \Delta\text{SRT}_i. \tag{11}$$

The estimated threshold is calculated according to Brand and Kollmeier (2002), which fits a single psychometric function to the entire track.

Identifying the smallest absolute threshold difference with the KIC was important, as the simulation included consistently distracted tracks [large a in Eq. (9)]. This way, all consistent tracks had a small absolute KIC, while larger values corresponded to a higher impact of two psychometric functions on the track.

KIC can take on both positive and negative values. The sign indicates whether the SRT is over or underestimated because of an inconsistency in the track. If we find a consistency measure that is a good predictor of the signed KIC, we can correct inconsistent measurements. To find out if this is possible, we compared several candidates for consistency measures with both signed and unsigned (i.e., the absolute value of the KIC).

B. Candidates for a consistency measure

A set of candidates for consistency measures was defined and compared with the KIC.

- Standard deviation σ after the second reversal point n_{rev} ,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= \text{SD}(\{r_{n_{\text{rev}}}, \dots, r_{N-1}\}), \\ \sigma_s &= \text{SD}(\{s_{n_{\text{rev}}}, \dots, s_{N-1}\}). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

- Slope m of a linear interpolation of the track after the second reversal point,

$$\begin{aligned} m_r &= \text{slope}(\{r_{n_{\text{rev}}}, \dots, r_{N-1}\}), \\ m_s &= \text{slope}(\{s_{n_{\text{rev}}}, \dots, s_{N-1}\}). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

- Resonance frequency f of the track after the second reversal point,

$$\begin{aligned} f_r &= \underset{f}{\text{argmax}}(|\mathcal{F}\{r_{n_{\text{rev}}}, \dots, r_{N-1}\}|), \\ f_s &= \underset{f}{\text{argmax}}(|\mathcal{F}\{s_{n_{\text{rev}}}, \dots, s_{N-1}\}|). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

\mathcal{F} stands for the discrete Fourier transformation. $|\dots|$ is the absolute value.

- Slope m' of a linear interpolation to the absolute value of the spectrum of the track after the second reversal point,

$$\begin{aligned} m'_r &= \text{slope}(|\mathcal{F}\{r_{n_{\text{rev}}}, \dots, r_{N-1}\}|), \\ m'_s &= \text{slope}(|\mathcal{F}\{s_{n_{\text{rev}}}, \dots, s_{N-1}\}|). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

- Bootstrapped consistency measure: The standard deviation of the threshold distribution generated by a bootstrapping procedure.
- The single psychometric function goodness of fit measure (SiPGOF).

All candidates for a consistency measure except SiPGOF and bootstrapped consistency measure were calculated for the part of the track that came after the second reversal point of the track. This was done to make the consistency measure less sensitive to the initial stimulus level of the measurement procedure.

For the bootstrapped consistency measure, the threshold distribution of a maximum likelihood fit with a single psychometric function according to Brand and Kollmeier (2002) was calculated from 100 random samples of the original track. Each sample consisted of 20 random draws (with replacement) from the 20 trials in the original track. The standard deviation of the resulting distribution of thresholds was evaluated. It indicates how consistently a single psychometric function can describe the track.

C. Assessment of consistency measures with expert-labeled tracks

The candidates for a consistency measure were compared to expert-labeled tracks of adaptive matrix sentence

tests. Two independent experts with long experience in psychometric measurements with the matrix test were asked to rate the outcome of US-English and Cantonese matrix sentence tests with a traffic light color coding. Green stood for consistent (group 0), orange resembled questionable consistency (group 1), and red stood for a clearly inconsistent measurement (group 2). The matrix sentence tests included Lombard and plain speech, i.e., speech with raised and normal vocal effort [see Scharf *et al.* (2022)], in the following noise conditions (ascending order of difficulty):

- Unmodulated speech noise with a long-term spectrum of a male speaker at normal vocal effort (Dreschler *et al.*, 2001) (ICRA1-noise).
- Modulated ICRA1 noise with a duration of pauses no longer than 250 ms (Wagener *et al.*, 2006) (ICRA5-250).
- Multi-talker babble noise.
- ICRA1-noise noise in reverberation ($t_{60} = 2.69$ s).

The reverb condition had the effect that several subjects performed well at the beginning but lost the cue, after which they continuously performed worse than at the beginning of the test.

The Spearman correlation coefficient (R) of the expert rating with the consistency measures was calculated alongside the area under the curve (AUC) of the receiver operating characteristic (ROC), which was mirrored on the diagonal if the true positive rate was smaller than the false positive rate. This way $AUC \geq 0.5$. For the ROC, the expert rating was defined as ground truth. For this, the three levels of expert rating were merged into two groups (0 and 1 + 2). This was done because groups 1 and 2 were an order of magnitude smaller than group 0, and there was no significant difference in SiPGOF between 1 and 2 (see Fig. 4).

For the calculation of SiPGOF for the expert-labeled tracks, the following boundary conditions were used for all word specific psychometric functions [see Eq. (3): $\gamma = 0.1$, $\lambda = 0$, $\text{slope} = 14.25\%/dB$ [average of US-English and Cantonese matrix sentence test (Kollmeier *et al.*, 2015; Hu *et al.*, 2024)]].

D. Consistency of unlabeled tracks

Unrated matrix sentence tracks from Schädler *et al.* (2020) and Hülsmeier (2022) were used to derive a classification threshold for the consistency of tracks of the matrix sentence test. The tracks were for German, male matrix sentence tests in ICRA1-noise, ICRA5-250, and babble talker noise with the adaptive procedure of Brand and Kollmeier (2002). The boundary condition for the psychometric function of SiPGOF was adjusted to the average slope of the German, male matrix sentence test of 17.1%/dB (Kollmeier *et al.*, 2015).

The classification threshold was estimated with a histogram of SiPGOF for a target classification rate. The SiPGOF threshold has been selected such that the cumulative probability of SiPGOF is equal to the target true

positive rate of the test (i.e., truly consistent classified as consistent, see Appendix B).

III. RESULTS

A. Best consistency measure to predict simulated inconsistent tracks

The upper panel of Table I contains the R of the consistency measures candidates, the AUC of a classification with the KIC for simulated, inconsistent tracks for both signed and unsigned KIC. A track with $|KIC| < 1$ dB was classified as consistent. No candidate for the consistency measures showed a high correlation with the signed KIC.

The ROC-curve for a classification with the unsigned KIC is shown in Fig. 3(a) for the best and worst performing consistency measures. The single psychometric function goodness of fit measure (SiPGOF) and bootstrapping method showed the highest AUC, followed by the standard deviation of \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{s} after the second reversal. The spectral slope of \mathbf{s} after the second reversal m'_s was not a good indicator of inconsistency.

The bootstrapping method was the computationally most expensive measure because it included 100 fits of a single psychometric function to samples of the track. This made the bootstrapping method the slowest measure to compute, followed by SiPGOF, which required two fits.

B. Best consistency measure to predict expert ratings

The experts agreed with a Kendall τ_B correlation of 0.77. Figure 4 shows the distribution of expert ratings and SiPGOF, which is the most promising consistency measure for simulated, inconsistent tracks. Tracks that were labeled as consistent (group 0) showed a significant difference in SiPGOF to tracks that were not labeled as consistent (group 1 + 2). No significant difference existed between groups 1 and 2 (questionable and unsuccessful).

The prediction results of expert ratings with consistency measures are displayed in the lower panel of Table I and the right panel of Fig. 3. Of all consistency measures considered, the spectral slope m'_s was the best predictor of expert ratings, outperforming SiPGOF, the standard deviation of \mathbf{s} ,

and the bootstrapped consistency measure. The standard deviation of \mathbf{r} was not a predictor of expert ratings.

C. Consistency of unlabeled tracks

SiPGOF was calculated for every unlabeled track of the German, male matrix sentence test of publicly available tracks (Schädler *et al.*, 2020; Hülsmeier, 2022). The histogram of the distribution of SiPGOF is displayed in Fig. 5.

From the expert-labeled database, which contained an elevated amount of inconsistent tracks, we can expect 15% or less inconsistent tracks in an unscreened database.

A retest of an inconsistent track doubles the duration of the experiment. Therefore, to keep the number of retests small, we propose a target of 80% correctly classified consistent tracks. For this, we can expect to correctly classify 60% of all inconsistent tracks in the simulation and estimate a threshold $SiPGOF \approx 10$ (see dashed line in Fig. 5 and Appendix B).

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Best consistency measure

SiPGOF was the best consistency measure among our tested candidates for simulated, inconsistent tracks. It had a slightly better true positive rate than a bootstrapping approach [see Fig. 3(a)] with equal AUC.

This is because the two measures share a related definition of consistency: a track is consistent if it agrees with a single psychometric function. However, the bootstrapped consistency measure can mislead in some cases because it cannot discriminate between random, but consistent variations and inconsistent response behavior: the response r_k is binomial distributed around the value of the psychometric function $\Phi(s_k)$ for the stimulus s_k (see Fig. 1). r_k can scatter substantially around the expected mean for a single underlying psychometric function. The bootstrapping approach will rate any deviation from $\Phi(s_k)$ as inconsistent. For SiPGOF only those deviations of r_k are counted as detrimental, which are in agreement with the effect of a distraction. Accordingly, the bootstrapped consistency measure is expected to have a reduced true positive rate (i.e., it rates more consistent tracks as inconsistent) in comparison to

TABLE I. Spearman correlation coefficient (R) and area under the curve (AUC) of consistency measures with KIC and expert rating.

See Eqs. (12)–(15)	SiPGOF	Standard deviation		Slope		Resonance frequency		Slope of spectrum		Bootstrapped consistency measure
		σ_s	σ_r	m_s	m_r	f_s	f_r	m'_s	m'_r	
R	0.16	0.07	0.17	-0.06	-0.05	Signed KIC		-0.00	0.08	0.13
R	0.39	0.27	0.32	-0.04	-0.04	Unsigned KIC		-0.09	0.02	0.38
AUC	0.78	0.69	0.74	0.56	0.54	0.53	0.55	0.62	0.56	0.76
R	0.29	0.23	0.04	-0.09	0.11	Ground truth from expert rating ^a		-0.22	-0.04	0.23
AUC	0.74	0.69	0.53	0.60	0.59	0.67	0.55	0.85	0.58	0.69

^aPrediction of expert ratings for empirical tracks.

FIG. 3. ROC for a classification of psychometric tracks of the matrix sentence test. σ is the standard deviation and m' is the slope of the spectrum [see Eqs. (15) and (12)]. Subscript s and r stand for stimulus and response, respectively. A consistent track is counted as positive. (a) classification of the KIC for a simulation of inconsistent tracks. (b) classification of expert rating for empirical tracks.

SiPGOF. This effect is observable for our simulation of inconsistent tracks and the prediction of expert ratings (see Fig. 3).

The slope and resonance frequency of s and r had no predictive value. However, measures of the fluctuations of the track, e.g., the standard deviation, or spectral slope of s and r, were above chance level. Still, the correlation with the KIC of the simulated tracks was smaller than for SiPGOF. This is in line with Smits et al. (2022), who found that measures of fluctuations of a track like the standard deviation are not sufficient to measure the consistency of the one-up one-down adaptive procedure.

The spectral slope of s was not the best consistency measure for simulated, inconsistent tracks. Valid tracks, although less common, may contain low frequency fluctuations of s. However, we found the spectral slope to be the best predictor of expert ratings [see Fig. 3(b)]. One possible explanation for this outcome is that large fluctuations in s are generally identified as inconsistency of a track (Smits et al., 2022). The spectral slope, or the standard deviation after the second reversal, measures this property.

However, the following reasons speak against the spectral slope of s as a consistency measure.

- It cannot generalize. Any measure of the fluctuations of the stimulus in a track will be misleading if the procedure exhibits oscillations that are not detrimental for the purpose of the measurement, e.g., experiments with constant

FIG. 4. Violin plot of SiPGOF for all expert rating groups. Relative frequency of occurrence as a vertical histogram including median, interquartile range, and empirical standard deviation. The expert rating is indicated by a traffic light color coding. Green (left) stands for consistent, orange resembles uncertain consistency, and red (right) stands for inconsistent tracks. Ratings are grouped 0–2. The significance level (Turkey’s test) is indicated with brackets, “***” is significant with $p < 10^{-3}$, “ns” is not significant.

FIG. 5. Histogram of SiPGOF for unlabeled German, male matrix tests. For the calculation of SiPGOF, both slopes of the psychometric functions were fixed to the average value for the German, male matrix sentence test. The dotted line points to the cumulative probability for SiPGOF = 10.

stimuli where a sequential response bias may cause a quasi-periodic cycle.

- It does not consider all information. The spectral slope of s ignores information about r .
- Experts may be biased. The expert rating may be biased to rate fluctuating tracks as inconsistent. Our simulation suggests this, since the spectral slope s was no good predictor of the KIC.

The standard deviation of r was no predictor of the expert ratings, even though it was shown in our simulation to contain useful information about the consistency of the track. This indicates that experts may overly rely on certain features (like the spectral slope of s), while other aspects are not considered. This is different from a model-based measure of consistency, like SiPGOF. SiPGOF weights all aspects of the track based on a model understanding of inconsistency. This may suggest the advantage of SiPGOF as support for expert decisions.

B. SiPGOF as local optimum

To compute the l_{max} the free parameters of the model were optimized with the EM algorithm. The EM/Baum-Welch algorithm is guaranteed to converge at a local and not a global optimum. In this application, the optimization was started at the 25th and 75th percentiles of the signal to noise ratio values in the track. Even if a track allows more than one local optimum, we believe a result near this starting point is an acceptable solution. Other starting points might be used in other applications.

C. Consistency measure as correction factor

For the simulated tracks, no consistency measure is correlated with the signed KIC (indicating over- or underestimation of the SRT; see Table I). This is because there is no defined order of states: a continuously distracted subject may produce relatively consistent tracks with high SRT. The tested consistency measures were unable to point out which state is the unwanted state of the subject; only the existence of two rivaling states can be indicated. This means that if an inconsistent track is identified, it cannot be corrected without further assumptions, e.g., the assumption that the true SRT is below or above the estimated threshold.

SiPGOF had the highest correlation with the KIC (see Table I). The KIC of the simulated, inconsistent tracks is defined as the mismatch between the estimated threshold and the threshold of the underlying psychometric function (see Sec. II). Out of all tested consistency measures, SiPGOF is the most promising correction factor for inconsistent threshold estimates.

D. Definition of a classification threshold from unlabeled data

To use SiPGOF as a binary classifier, a rejection criterion needs to be known. We can estimate this threshold with a histogram of SiPGOF for unrated measurements (see Fig. 5).

The threshold is estimated from the cumulative distribution of SiPGOF (Fig. 5) and the ROC of the simulation (left panel of Fig. 3). From this, we estimate a lower bound for the true positive rate of 80% (i.e., truly consistent rated as consistent) for a threshold of SiPGOF = 10 (dotted line in Fig. 5) because the dataset was not guaranteed to only contain consistent tracks. From simulation, we can expect SiPGOF to classify 6 out of 10 truly inconsistent tracks as inconsistent for this threshold (see Appendix B). Therefore, we recommend using the rejection criterion of SiPGOF > 10 for the German, male matrix sentence test.

Threshold values for SiPGOF with other psychometric tests are derived the same way. However, if no simulation with KIC is available, only the true positive rate (i.e., truly consistent rated as consistent) can be calculated.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We conclude that the single psychometric function goodness of fit measure (SiPGOF) can rate simulated tracks correctly and encode important information about the consistency of a track to support experts. SiPGOF should be preferred over a bootstrapping approach because of the theoretically more efficient calculation and a larger true positive rate (i.e., truly consistent rated as consistent), which is favorable for rare occurrences of inconsistent tracks.

SiPGOF encodes a different definition of inconsistency than the spectral slope of the s , which is a better predictor of expert ratings. The predictability of expert ratings with the spectral slope of s indicates that experts may be biased in their rating towards large fluctuations in the track. This emphasizes the need for a model-based consistency measure.

We present a method to estimate a suitable SiPGOF threshold with unlabeled tracks and find a suitable value to be 10 for the German, male matrix sentence test for a 60% chance to correctly classify inconsistent tracks as inconsistent and a false alarm rate of 20%.

A clear limitation of this study is that for any empirical data there is no well-defined ground truth, i.e., some indication about how consistent the subjects actually were able to respond to the psychometric measurement. Monitoring the subjects' performance with EEG, pupil dilation, or purposely exhaustive measurement sessions might help to further verify the presented consistency measures.

In conclusion, while it is challenging to establish a meaningful ground truth of consistency, SiPGOF appears to be a promising candidate for a model-based measure of the consistency of psychometric measurements.

VI. OUTLOOK

The proposed consistency measure could be applied to the following use cases.

A. Indicator for breaks

Exhaustion of test subjects during extensive tests can increase the rate of inconsistent responses due to a

continuous lapse in attention. Modern measurement procedures should be robust against inconsistent response behavior or suggest an option to overcome this problem, i.e., repeat the measurement, take a break, or terminate the session (to be resumed later). A consistency measure might therefore indicate that a break is beneficial.

B. Quality screening

Machine learning approaches with psychometric data (Saak *et al.*, 2022) require a large amount of data from high-quality measurements. Crowdsourcing with self-administered tests is a possible approach to generating the necessary amount of data. However, to be useful, a quality control has to exist (Allahbakhsh *et al.*, 2013). Presently, trained specialists are required for monitoring tests. Furthermore, if the monitoring results are not available at run time, the likelihood of a consistent retest is low. For automated procedures, an objective definition of consistency and a range of acceptable values of this rating have to be defined. We have reported an appropriate value of the classification threshold for the German matrix sentence test.

C. Expert support system

In clinical practice of psychometric measurements, as performed by, e.g., audiologists, an objective quality control may be beneficial. This has been discussed by Smits *et al.* (2022) for the one-up, one-down adaptive staircase procedure. They showed that the consistency of an adaptive measurement is independent of the rate of convergence to the threshold stimulus, i.e., how smoothly the stimulus converged to the anticipated threshold. With no clear definition of consistency, rating the consistency of psychometric data remains a highly subjective task for the experimenter. Consequently, experimenters may be biased in their rating by the visual representation of the track (see example in Fig. 1). Our simulations indicate that a model-based consistency measure may provide relevant information in a clinical setting.

D. Test optimization

Unoptimized speech tests vary in threshold between sentences. This results in a smearing of the estimated psychometric function because of a superposition of various psychometric functions with different thresholds (Kollmeier, 1990). We have shown that SiPGOF can be used to distinguish between one and two psychometric functions. The consistency measure may be used to optimize speech tests without the need for human subjects when used together with computational models of speech intelligibility, such as the framework of auditory discrimination experiments (FADE) (Schädler *et al.*, 2015). A bootstrapped consistency measure is already included in FADE. However, our empirical data did not include heterogeneous (i.e., unoptimized) speech tests to test the consistency measure explicitly as a predictor of homogeneity.

E. Consistency measure for non-converging measurement procedures

Psychometric measurements do not necessarily aim to converge at a constant response, as there needs to be a trade-off between the number of trials (i.e., responses during a full test) and the time needed to complete the measurement.

This is why modern procedures heavily rely on assumptions about the psychometric function and only query stimuli with maximum expected gain of new information (Brand and Kollmeier, 2002; Doire *et al.*, 2017; Schlittenlacher *et al.*, 2018). However, this comes at a cost: inconsistent responses at the beginning of the test can misguide the procedure. Interleaved procedures can monitor the performance of a subject (Leek *et al.*, 1991) by concurrent estimates of the threshold, but lead to longer measurements. Additionally, if the procedure does not aim to converge, inconsistent measurements are harder to detect by visual inspection. As a result, inconsistent tracks of these procedures are difficult to recognize without an objective consistency measure.

F. Future extensions

The SiPGOF presented here includes the comparison of a single-state to a two-state model. Future extensions of the SiPGOF may be generalized to more states. A Bayesian version might then automatically find the smallest number of states needed for a given track, by its inherent Occam's Razor mechanism [see Occam factor (MacKay (2006), Chap. 28)].

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors report no conflict of interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Empirical tracks of the German matrix sentence test are available in Hülsmeier (2022). SiPGOF is implemented in PYTHON and supplements this article (Scharf, 2025).

NOMENCLATURE

γ	Guess rate
λ	Lapse rate
l_{\max}	Maximum log-likelihood
\mathbf{r}	Sequence of responses
\mathbf{s}	Sequence of stimuli
AUC	Area under the curve
dB	Decibel
EM	Expectation maximization
FADE	Framework of auditory discrimination experiments
ICRA1-noise	Unmodulated speech noise with a long-term spectrum of a male speaker at normal vocal effort
ICRA5-250	Modulated ICRA1 noise with a duration of pauses no longer than 250ms
KIC	Known inconsistency
R	Spearman correlation coefficient
ROC	Receiver operating characteristic
SiPGOF	The single psychometric function goodness of fit measure
SRT	Speech recognition threshold

APPENDIX A: GUESS-RATE OF THE MATRIX SENTENCE TEST

For the closed matrix sentence test, the sentence-specific guess rate and the word-specific guess rate are identical, which may lead to confusion of the two. Guessing a word from 10 choices results in a word-specific guess rate of 0.1, while guessing a sentence from a 5-word sentence (trial) yields a sentence-specific guess rate of

$$\frac{1}{5} \sum_{i=0}^5 (5-i) \binom{5}{i} 0.1^{5-i} \cdot 0.9^i = 0.1. \tag{A1}$$

This means that a test subject of the forced-choice matrix sentence test can on average never score worse than 1/2 word correct out of a sentence. Although there is no difference in the guess rate, the underlying psychometric functions are not identical, as the slope of the sentence-specific psychometric function cannot be steeper than the slope of the word-specific psychometric function [for implications of this on test development, see Kollmeier *et al.* (2015)].

APPENDIX B: REJECTION CRITERION

The rejection criterion was calculated from the ROC of simulated, inconsistent tracks and a histogram of SiPGOF for unlabeled empirical matrix tests from Schädler *et al.* (2020) and Hülsmeier (2022). The ROC maps false-positive rate (p_{FP} , i.e., inconsistent tracks were falsely identified as consistent) to true-positive rate (p_{TP} , i.e., consistent tracks were correctly identified as consistent),

$$\text{ROC: } p_{FP} \rightarrow p_{TP}. \tag{B1}$$

FIG. 6. SiPGOF threshold and estimated true positive rate. Black: map of false positive rate to threshold SiPGOF according to Eq. (B4). Red: ROC of SiPGOF for simulated inconsistent tracks as in Fig. 3(a). The vertical, dotted line marks the estimated performance of a consistency test with a threshold SiPGOF = 10.

From the distribution of SiPGOF for unlabeled, empirical tracks, we can estimate the cumulative distribution H to classify a track as consistent (i.e., the probability of a track to have a SiPGOF below the threshold above which tracks are considered inconsistent; see Fig. 5),

$$H: \text{SiPGOF} \rightarrow p_{\text{consistent}}. \tag{B2}$$

If we assume that the number of inconsistent tracks in the empirical data is small, we can approximate

$$p_{\text{consistent}} \approx p_{TP}. \tag{B3}$$

The cumulative probability function H [Eqs. (B2)] is bijective (see Fig. 5), so we can invert it and substitute into Eq. (B1),

$$p_{FP} \rightarrow \text{SiPGOF}_{\text{threshold}}. \tag{B4}$$

The function (B4) is shown in Fig. 6 in black. A threshold of $\text{SiPGOF} \approx 10$ yields a true positive rate of $p_{TP} \approx 0.8$ (8 out of 10 consistent tracks are correctly classified as consistent) and a false positive rate of $p_{FP} \approx 0.4$ (four out of ten inconsistent tracks are not identified as such).

If SiPGOF is used to test for inconsistency, this test will have a sensitivity (inconsistent classified as inconsistent) of $\approx 60\%$ and a specificity (consistent classified as consistent) of $\approx 80\%$.

Allahbakhsh, M., Benatallah, B., Ignjatovic, A., Motahari-Nezhad, H. R., Bertino, E., and Dustdar, S. (2013). "Quality control in crowdsourcing systems: Issues and directions," *IEEE Internet Comput.* **17**(2), 76–81.

Bianco, R., Mills, G., de Kerangal, M., Rosen, S., and Chait, M. (2021). "Reward enhances online participants' engagement with a demanding auditory task," *Trends Hear.* **25**, 233121652110259.

Bishop, C. M. (2009). *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*, Information Science and Statistics (Springer Science + Business Media, New York).

Brand, T., and Kollmeier, B. (2002). "Efficient adaptive procedures for threshold and concurrent slope estimates for psychophysics and speech intelligibility tests," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **111**(6), 2801–2810.

- Doire, C. S. J., Brookes, M., and Naylor, P. A. (2017). "Robust and efficient Bayesian adaptive psychometric function estimation," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **141**(4), 2501–2512.
- Dreschler, W. A., Verschuure, H., Ludvigsen, C., and Westermann, S. (2001). "ICRA Noises: Artificial Noise Signals with Speech-like Spectral and Temporal Properties for Hearing Instrument Assessment: Ruidos ICRA: Señales de ruido artificial con espectro similar al habla y propiedades temporales para pruebas de instrumentos auditivos," *Int. J. Audiol.* **40**(3), 148–157.
- Frund, I., Haenel, N. V., and Wichmann, F. A. (2011). "Inference for psychometric functions in the presence of nonstationary behavior," *J. Vision* **11**(6), 16.
- Hu, H., Hochmuth, S., Man, C. K., Warzybok, A., Kollmeier, B., and Wong, L. L. N. (2024). "Development and evaluation of the Cantonese matrix sentence test," *Int. J. Audiol.* **63**, 8–20.
- Hülsmeier, D. (2022). "d-hr/hz-2020-data-drop: Initial data drop," Github repository, <http://10.5281/ZENODO.6481185>
- Kollmeier, B. (1990). "Meßmethodik, Modellierung und Verbesserung der Verständlichkeit von Sprache" ("Measurement methodology, modeling, and improvement of speech intelligibility"), Ph.D. thesis, Göttingen University, Göttingen, Germany.
- Kollmeier, B., Warzybok, A., Hochmuth, S., Zokoll, M. A., Usilar, V., Brand, T., and Wagener, K. C. (2015). "The multilingual matrix test: Principles, applications, and comparison across languages: A review," *Int. J. Audiol.* **54**(sup2), 3–16.
- Leek, M. R. (2001). "Adaptive procedures in psychophysical research," *Percept. Psychophys.* **63**(8), 1279–1292.
- Leek, M. R., Hanna, T. E., and Marshall, L. (1991). "An interleaved tracking procedure to monitor unstable psychometric functions," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **90**(3), 1385–1397.
- MacKay, D. J. (2006). *Information Theory, Inference and Learning Algorithms* (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK).
- Ooster, J., Krueger, M., Bach, J.-H., Wagener, K. C., Kollmeier, B., and Meyer, B. T. (2020). "Speech audiometry at home: Automated listening tests via smart speakers with normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners," *Trends Hear.* **24**, 233121652097001.
- Rabiner, L. (1989). "A tutorial on hidden Markov models and selected applications in speech recognition," *Proc. IEEE* **77**(2), 257–286.
- Saak, S., Hülsmeier, D., Kollmeier, B., and Buhl, M. (2022). "A flexible data-driven audiological patient stratification method for deriving auditory profiles," *Front. Neurol.* **13**, 959582.
- Schädler, M. R., Hülsmeier, D., Warzybok, A., and Kollmeier, B. (2020). "Individual aided speech-recognition performance and predictions of benefit for listeners with impaired hearing employing FADE," *Trends Hear.* **24**, 233121652093892.
- Schädler, M. R., Warzybok, A., Hochmuth, S., and Kollmeier, B. (2015). "Matrix sentence intelligibility prediction using an automatic speech recognition system," *Int. J. Audiol.* **54**(2), 100–107.
- Scharf, M. K. (2025). "maxamazing/sipgof: Single psychometric function goodness of fit measure," <http://10.5281/ZENODO.10277694>.
- Scharf, M. K., Hochmuth, S., Wong, L. N., Kollmeier, B., and Warzybok, A. (2022). "Lombard effect for bilingual speakers in Cantonese and English: Importance of spectro-temporal features," in *Proceedings of Interspeech 2022*, edited by H. Ko and J. H. L. Hansen (ISCA, Incheon, South Korea).
- Schlittenlacher, J., Turner, R. E., and Moore, B. C. J. (2018). "Audiogram estimation using Bayesian active learning," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **144**(1), 421–430.
- Smits, C., Festen, J. M., Swanepoel, D. W., Moore, D. R., and Dillon, H. (2022). "The one-up one-down adaptive (staircase) procedure in speech-in-noise testing: Standard error of measurement and fluctuations in the track," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **152**(4), 2357–2368.
- Swanepoel, D. W., Clark, J. L., Koekemoer, D., Hall, J. W., III, Krumm, M., Ferrari, D. V., McPherson, B., Olusanya, B. O., Mars, M., Russo, I., and Barajas, J. J. (2010). "Telehealth in audiology: The need and potential to reach underserved communities," *Int. J. Audiol.* **49**(3), 195–202.
- Swanepoel, D. W., and Hall, J. W. (2010). "A systematic review of telehealth applications in audiology," *Telemed. e-Health* **16**(2), 181–200.
- Treutwein, B. (1995). "Adaptive psychophysical procedures," *Vision Res.* **35**(17), 2503–2522.
- Virtanen, P., Gommers, R., Oliphant, T. E., Haberland, M., Reddy, T., Cournapeau, D., Burovski, E., Peterson, P., Weckesser, W., Bright, J., van der Walt, S. J., Brett, M., Wilson, J., Millman, K. J., Mayorov, N., Nelson, A. R. J., Jones, E., Kern, R., Larson, E., Carey, C. J., Polat, İ., Feng, Y., Moore, E. W., VanderPlas, J., Laxalde, D., Perktold, J., Cimman, R., Henriksen, I., Quintero, E. A., Harris, C. R., Archibald, A. M., Ribeiro, A. H., Pedregosa, F., van Mulbregt, P., and SciPy 1.0 Contributors (2020). "SciPy 1.0: Fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python," *Nat. Methods* **17**, 261–272.
- Wagener, K. C., Brand, T., and Kollmeier, B. (2006). "The role of silent intervals for sentence intelligibility in fluctuating noise in hearing-impaired listeners," *Int. J. Audiol.* **45**(1), 26–33.
- Xu, C., Hülsmeier, D., Buhl, M., and Kollmeier, B. (2024). "How does inattention influence the robustness and efficiency of adaptive procedures in the context of psychoacoustic assessments via smartphone?," *Trends Hear.* **28**, 23312165241288051.